

Error modeling and parameter identification of a 5-DOF hybrid robot considering angular transmission error

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Abstract

The forms of angular transmission error are complex and diverse, and it is difficult to derive the error model theoretically. Therefore, the geometric error and angular transmission error are generally studied respectively by neglecting the interference of these errors. In this paper, a novel mixed error model(MEM) combining the fitting model and the theoretical model is derived, which is formed by adding the mixed angular transmission error model to the geometric error model in the form of joint extension positioning error. The mixed angular transmission error model is derived based on the fitting angular transmission error and geometric error interference analysis in uniaxial experiments. In the identification process, the angular transmission error under uniaxial experimental measurement is first measured and fitted, and then the geometric error and angular transmission error are identified simultaneously based on the MEM. A 5-DOF hybrid robot is used as an example to verify the error modeling method and parameter identification process. Based on the error modeling method and parameter identification scheme, the robot's motion error is dropped by more than 50% compared with the geometric error identification scheme.

Keywords: error modeling, geometric error, angular transmission error, parameter identification, hybrid robot.

1. Introduction

Industrial robots are of great significance in modern manufacturing, and kinematic calibration is an important way to improve the accuracy of industrial robots[1]. Kinematic calibration involves the procedures of error modeling, measurement, identification, and compensation. Among these pro-cedures, error modeling is the theoretical basis and plays an important role in the calibration[2].

Error modeling is classified into two levels according to the range of the error parameters to be identified[3]. One level is the geometric error model, which covers the overall geometric parameters of the robot mechanism. The errors of the overall geometry, such as the length of the links, the direction of the joint rotational axes, and the propagation error of the joint parameters, are considered. The other is the joint error model, which deals with the identification of joint variables of the kinematic error model such as the backlash error and the angular transmission error[4].

The geometric error modeling has been widely studied and the commonly used model is the D-H error model based on Denavit-Hartenberg (D-H) parameters[5]. However, the D-H error model does not meet the continuity requirements when the robot has approximate parallel axes. Hayati built a modified D-H model which adds an additional rotation parameter to the Y-axis[6]. Zhuang and Roth proposed a CPC modeling method to continuously derive the relationship between arbitrary frames in space using six parameters[7]. The local product of exponential (local POE) error model satisfies completeness, continuity and minimality after eliminating redundant parameters through theoretical or numerical methods[8, 9, 10]. However, the aforementioned geometric model does not take into account common joint errors such as joint backlash and angular transmission errors.

Backlash error is commonly found in mechanical transmission where inherent clearance is unavoidable in the gearbox of joint[11]. In the error modeling process, Backlash error is often assumed to be a function of joint speed or displacement, which mainly varies with the direction of joint speed[12, 13, 14]. Ruderman et al. built a backlash error model of a single joint, which needs the angle difference between the motor side encoder value and the link side additional encoder value to identify its parameters[12]. Their approach is complex for practical application due to the requirement of a high precision encoder on the link side. Slamani et al. established a 2-order polynomial model for the backlash error[15], which measures tool center point(TCP) relative distance error throughout bidirectional linear paths to identify its parameters. But, the impact of geometric error is not considered. Webb et al. proposed the backlash error model of all joints of the robot, which was combined with the geometric error model and used the same parameter identification method as geometric error identification[16, 17, 18].

Angular transmission error is the nonlinear variation of the difference between the nominal and actual joint displacement. Due to the different characteristics and wear of robot joint reducers, the characteristics of angular transmission error are also varied. There is no unified theoretical error model to describe it. Therefore, the angular transmission error is usually fitted as a harmonic function of the joint displacement[19, 20]. There are a few approaches to measure and fit the angular transmission error. One approach is based on independent rotating motor gearbox systems like harmonic gearbox or cycloidal pinwheel gearbox and the angular transmission error is calculated from the angle difference between the motor side encoder value and the link side[21, 22, 23], which requires disassembling the robotic arm. Another approach is based on installing measuring equipment on the robotic arm and the angular transmission error is calculated from the TCP movement error[24]. However, the operation of installing measuring equipment on every robotic arm link is cumbersome and dangerous [25].

In general, there is a lack of error identification methods that consider geometric errors and angular transmission error together. The latest study[5], based on the R-Test instrument, measures both angular positioning deviations and geometric error, but still did not account for angular transmission error. This is mainly because geometric errors tend to be identified by theoretical methods, whereas angular transmission errors tend to be identified by fitting methods. However, the mutual interference between the two in the identification process affects the accuracy of identification[26]. In this paper, 1) a new Mixed Error Model (MEM) combining fitting model and theoretical model is proposed, which is formed by adding the mixed angle transmission error model to the geometric error model in the form of joint extension positioning error, addressing the issue of neglecting the interference between geometric errors and angular transmission errors. 2) The mixed angular transmission error model is derived based on the fitting angular transmission error and geometric error interferometric analysis in uniaxial experiments, which solves the inherent difficulty of deriving the angular transmission error model theoretically due to the com-

plex form of angular transmission error. Experiments are carried out on a 5-DOF hybrid robot to demonstrate its precision and effectiveness.

2. Error modeling method and identification scheme

2.1. Geometric error modeling

The geometric error model of the robot is derived from the local POE formula. The procedures of error modeling based on the local POE formula in a dyad are illustrated in Figure 1. Links j and $j + 1$ are adjacent and connected by the joint $j + 1$, and q_{j+1} denotes actual joint displacement of the joint $j + 1$. The local coordinate frame $\{\mathbf{R}_j\}$ is attached to the proximal end of link j , and another local coordinate frame $\{\mathbf{F}_{j+1}\}$ is attached to the distal end of link j . According to the local POE formula, the relative poses between two consecutive local proximal frames $\{\mathbf{R}_j\}$ and $\{\mathbf{R}_{j+1}\}$ can be written as:

$$\mathbf{T}_j(q_{j+1}) = \mathbf{g}_j \mathbf{u}_{j+1} = \exp(\xi_j) \exp(\zeta_{j+1} q_{j+1}) \quad (1)$$

where the twist coordinates $\xi_j \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 1}$ is the coordinate of the distal end of link j with respect to $\{\mathbf{R}_j\}$, $\zeta_j \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 1}$ is the coordinate of the joint $j + 1$ with respect to $\{\mathbf{F}_{j+1}\}$ the sign “ \wedge ” represents the transformation of a given screw ξ from $\mathbb{R}^{6 \times 1}$ to $se(3)$, or from \mathbb{R}^3 to $so(3)$, $g_j = \exp(\xi_j) \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}$ denotes the homogeneous transformation matrix (HTM) between $\{\mathbf{R}_j\}$ and $\{\mathbf{F}_{j+1}\}$, and $u_j = \exp(\zeta_j) \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}$ denotes the HTM between $\{\mathbf{F}_{j+1}\}$ and $\{\mathbf{R}_{j+1}\}$. Therefore, the error model of relative poses between the actual $\{\mathbf{R}_{j+1}\}$ and nominal $\{\mathbf{R}_{j+1}^0\}$ with the error of the twist coordinates ξ_j and the joint displacement q_{j+1} can be written as[27]:

$$\delta e_j = A_j \delta \xi_j + Ad(\mathbf{g}_j \mathbf{u}_{j+1}) \zeta_{j+1} \delta q_{j+1} \quad (2)$$

where the operation $Ad(g)$ represents the adjoint transformation of g (For $Ad(g) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{d} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{R} \end{bmatrix} \in SE(3)$, the result of its $Ad()$ operation is $g = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{R} & \mathbf{0} \\ \hat{\mathbf{R}} & \mathbf{R} \end{bmatrix} \in SE(3)$ is the rotation matrix, and d is the column matrix of the translation vector. The coefficient matrix $A_j = I_6 + a_1 Z_j + a_2 Z_j^2 + a_3 Z_j^3 + a_4 Z_j^4$. If the joint j is a revolute joint, then the coefficients are as follows: $a_1 = \frac{4 - \beta_j \sin \beta_j - 4 \cos \beta_j}{2\beta_j^2}$, $a_2 = \frac{4\beta_j - 5 \sin \beta_j + \beta_j \cos \beta_j}{2\beta_j^3}$, $a_3 = \frac{2 - \beta_j \sin \beta_j - 2 \cos \beta_j}{2\beta_j^4}$, $a_4 = \frac{2\beta_j - 3 \sin \beta_j + \beta_j \cos \beta_j}{2\beta_j^5}$, where β_j is the sum of the squares of the first three digits of ξ_j . Z_j is the adjoint transformation of $\xi_j = [\omega^\top, \mathbf{v}^\top]$ and is given as $Ad(Z_j) = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\omega} & \mathbf{d} \\ \mathbf{0} & \hat{\omega} \end{bmatrix}$. Based on Eq. (2), the local POE formula for the forward kinematics of limb i can be written as:

$${}^i T_{0,j+1} = {}^i \mathbf{g}_0 {}^i \mathbf{u}_1 {}^i \mathbf{g}_1 {}^i \mathbf{u}_2 \dots {}^i \mathbf{u}_{n_i} {}^i \mathbf{g}_{n_i} \quad (3)$$

where n_i is the number of joints of the branch chain i . By differentiating Eq. (3), the geometric error model of the branch chain i can be written as:

$$\delta^i e_g = {}^i J \delta^i \rho + {}^i \Xi \delta^i q_a \quad (4)$$

Figure 1: Coordinate frames in a dyad

$$\begin{aligned}
{}^i \mathbf{J} &= [{}^i \mathbf{A}_{\rho,0}, Ad({}^i \mathbf{g}_0 {}^i \mathbf{u}_1) {}^i \mathbf{A}_{\rho,1}, \dots, Ad({}^i \mathbf{g}_{p0} \dots {}^i \mathbf{u}_{n_i}) {}^i \mathbf{A}_{\rho,n_i}] \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6n_i}, \\
{}^i \Xi &= [{}^i \zeta_0, Ad({}^i \mathbf{g}_0) {}^i \zeta_1, \dots, Ad({}^i \mathbf{g}_0 \dots {}^i \mathbf{u}_{n_i}) {}^i \zeta_j] \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times n_i}, \\
\delta^i \boldsymbol{\rho} &= [\delta^i \boldsymbol{\rho}_0^\top \dots \delta^i \boldsymbol{\rho}_{n_i}^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{6(n_i+1) \times 1}, \\
\delta^i \mathbf{q}_a &= [{}^i q_1, \dots, {}^i q_{n_i}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i \times 1}.
\end{aligned}$$

2.2. Backlash error modeling

Backlash is defined as a component of bidirectional repeatability. Figure 2 shows a mathematical model of backlash between the encoder angle and the joint angle. The joint angle will not change until the encoder angle catches up with the joint angle (from $q_{j,a}$ to $q_{j,b}$). Upon a motion reversal of the encoder angle, the encoder angle and joint angle will not be the same until the encoder angle catches up with the joint angle again. To simplify the calculation, it is assumed that the nominal transmission ratio that $k_n = 1$, so that the error of the joint actual angle q_{ob} can be directly represented by the error of the encoder angle q_{eb} (as shown in Figure 2). $q_{e,j+1}$ is the encoder readings in the current pose and $q_{e,j}$ is the encoder reading when the robot is in the previous pose. Let $q_{e,inc} = q_{e,j+1} - q_{e,j}$ and the joint backlash error q_{ab} can be written as:

$$q_{ab} = \begin{cases} -\text{sign}(q_{e,inc})q_{eb} & |q_{e,inc}| > q_{eb} \\ 0 & |q_{e,inc}| < q_{eb} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where q_{eb} is the maximum value of backlash error.

2.3. Mixed Angular transmission error modeling

Angular transmission error is the nonlinear part of the difference between nominal and actual joint displacement. It is mainly caused by the gear profile error and gearbox assembly error. Different gearbox manufacturing and assembly errors have different nonlinear effects on angular transmission error, which means the angular transmission error can not be described using deterministic formula directly. The angular transmission error of an assembled robot is commonly obtained based on the ideal trajectory and actual trajectory of the end-effector. Based on serial robot motion characteristics: the trajectory of the end-effector is always arc-shaped when only one revolute joint moves. As shown in Figure 3, let $l(q_{e,1}-q_{e,2})$ be the length of the arc ($q_{e,1}-q_{e,2}$)

Figure 2: Effect of the backlash errors on joint movement.

when the joint moves from $q_{e,1}$ to $q_{e,2}$ and R_l be the radius of fitting circle. Based on spatial circle fitting[28], it's easy to get the real joint displacement from $l(q_{e,1} - q_{e,2})/R_l$. The angular transmission error of the gearbox is always related to the gear manufacturing and assembly errors and it changes periodically with the movement of the joint. Although it's hard to get deterministic expressions of $Q_s(q_e)$ directly, the angular transmission error in the form of Fourier series can be written as:

$$Q_s(q_e) = \sum_{k=1}^{n_f} (a_k \sin(k\omega q_e) + b_k \cos(k\omega q_e)) \quad (6)$$

where ω , a_k and b_k are the coefficients of the Fourier series, and n_f is the order of the Fourier series. In previous studies[17, 26], the analysis of the measurement accuracy of $Q_{s,j}(q_{e,j})$ is generally ignored. However, due to the limitations of the mechanical structure, the joint cannot rotate 360° and the spatial circle fitting process would be unstable. A small change in one measurement point can cause a large change in the fitting result, which ultimately affects the measurement precision of the angular transmission errors. Besides, because of geometric error and backlash error, it's difficult to obtain the initial angle of the joint. Thus, the phase of angular transmission error is not accurate. Figure 4 is a 2-DOF robot used for example to compute the angle transmission error. Let the joint angle measured by the encoder be q_e , and the sum of the other errors (geometric error and the backlash error) be q_p . Let the difference between the real joint angle $q_e + q_p + Q_s$ and the joint angle measured by spatial circle fitting be q_m . The error of the circle fitting measurement angle can be expressed as:

$$\frac{q_m}{\delta r} = \frac{\sin(q_e + q_p + Q_s)}{\sqrt{R_l^2 + \delta r^2 - 2R_l \delta r \cos(q_e + q_p + Q_s)}} \quad (7)$$

where δr is the error caused by the geometric error between the center of the circle calculated by nominal inverse kinematics c_f and the actual center of the circle c_r (as shown in Figure 4), R_l is

Figure 3: Spatial circle fitting method.

Figure 4: Effect of spatial circle fitting error or geometric error on joint angle measurement.

the radius of the actual trajectory, and $Q_s + q_p \ll q_e, \delta r \ll R_l, \delta r/R_l (Q_s + q_p)$. So q_m can be transferred into a second-order form:

$$q_m = \frac{\sin(q_e)\delta r}{R_l} + \frac{\cos(q_e)\delta r}{R_l}(q_p + Q_s) \quad (8)$$

The measurement error of angular transmission error δQ_s obtained by the identification process can be expressed as:

$$\delta Q_s = q_m - Q_s = \left(1 - \frac{\cos(q_e)\delta r}{R_l}\right) Q_s + q_l \quad (9)$$

where

$$q_l = \frac{\sin(q_e)\delta r}{R_l} + \frac{\cos(q_e)\delta r}{R_l} q_p$$

The change period of q_l is longer than the angular transmission harmonic error, which is consistent with the joint rotation period. Therefore, the polynomial fitting method can be used to eliminate the trend term q_l before the fast fourier transform(FFT) of δQ_s . However, $\left(1 - \frac{\cos(q_e)\delta r}{R_l}\right) Q_s$ has the same changing period with Q_s , which affects the measurement accuracy of Q_s 's amplitude.

In the above analysis, the angular transmission error that includes only the Fourier series has a matching amplitude error and a matching phase error, which should be identified along with other errors to increase the discrimination accuracy. Therefore, a new angular transmission error model is proposed as:

$$Q_s(q_e) = A_s \sum_{k=1}^{n_f} (a_k \sin(k\omega(q_e + \phi_s)) + b_k \cos(k\omega(q_e + \phi_s))) \quad (10)$$

where A_s is the matching amplitude, and ϕ_s is the matching phase. Note that the matching phase and matching amplitude in Eq. (10) do not affect the Fourier series order. This modeling method is not affected by the complexity of the Fourier series and can be written as a fixed-form expression, and then both geometric and angular transmission errors can be written in first-order differential form.

2.4. Mixed error modeling and identification scheme

Under the assumptions $|q_{e,inc}| > q_{eb}$, the actual displacement $Q(q_e)_a$ of the joint with backlash error and angular transmission error can be expressed as:

$$Q_a(q_e) = q_0 + q_e - \text{sign}(q_{e,inc})q_{eb} + Q_s(q_e) \quad (11)$$

where q_0 is the joint displacement offset error, q_e is the joint encoder readings in the current pose, q_{eb} is the maximum joint backlash, and $Q(q_e)_s$ is the angular transmission error of this joint. By substituting Eq. 11) into Eq. (4), the extended geometric error model of the branch chain i which consists of geometric error, backlash error and angular transmission error can be written as:

$$\delta^i e = {}^i J \delta^i \rho + {}^i \Xi ({}^i Q_a(q_e) - q_e) + {}^i \Xi \delta^i Q_a(q_e) \quad (12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} {}^i\mathbf{Q}_a(\mathbf{q}_e) &= [\mathcal{Q}_{a,1}(q_{e,1}), \mathcal{Q}_{a,2}(q_{e,2}), \dots, \mathcal{Q}_{a,n_i}(q_{e,n_i})]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{n_i}, \\ \delta\mathcal{Q}_{a,j}(q_{e,j}) &= \delta q_{0,j} - \text{sign}(q_{e,inc,j})\delta q_{eb,j} + \delta\mathcal{Q}_{s,j}(q_{e,j}). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, these errors can be considered in the identification scheme together and the mutual interference of both errors is eliminated. The measurement error of angular transmission error model of the joint i can be expressed as:

$$\delta\mathcal{Q}_{a,i}(q_{e,i}) = \mathbf{J}_{q,i}\delta\rho_{q,i} \quad (13)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{J}_{q,i} &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial\mathcal{Q}_{s,i}}{\partial A_{s,i}} & \frac{\partial\mathcal{Q}_{s,i}}{\partial\phi_{s,i}} & -\text{sign}(q_{e,inc,j}) & 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^4, \\ \delta\rho_{q,i} &= [\delta\phi_{s,i}\delta A_{s,i}\delta q_{eb,i}\delta q_{0,i}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^4. \end{aligned}$$

By substituting Eq. (13) into Eq. (4), the error model of angular transmission error, backlash error and geometric error can be expressed as:

$$\delta\mathbf{e} = \mathbf{J}\delta\rho_g + \Xi\mathbf{J}_q\delta\rho_q + \Xi({}^i\mathbf{Q}_a(\mathbf{q}_e) - \mathbf{q}_e) \quad (14)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_q = \text{diag}([\mathbf{J}_{q,1} \quad \mathbf{J}_{q,2} \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{J}_{q,n}]) \in \mathbb{R}^{5 \times 5n}$, and $\delta\rho_q = [\delta\rho_{q,1} \quad \delta\rho_{q,2} \quad \dots \quad \delta\rho_{q,n}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{5n}$

Eq. (14) can be rewritten as:

$$\delta\mathbf{e}_c = \mathbf{J}_{all}\delta\rho_{all} \quad (15)$$

where $\delta\mathbf{e}_c = \delta\mathbf{e} - \Xi({}^i\mathbf{Q}_a(\mathbf{q}_e) - \mathbf{q}_e)$, $\mathbf{J}_{all} = [\mathbf{J} \quad \Xi\mathbf{J}_q] \in \mathbb{R}^{6[6n+1+5n]}$, and $\delta\rho_{all} = [\delta\rho_g, \delta\rho_q] \in \mathbb{R}^{6n+1+5n}$. Quadratic Regression (QR) redundant error elimination method is used to ensure that the corresponding row space of \mathbf{J}_{all} is stable with the selected experiment configurations[27]. The pivoted QR decomposition of \mathbf{J}_{all} can be written as:

$$\mathbf{J}_{all}\mathbf{P}_J = \mathbf{Q}_J \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{U}_J & \mathbf{K}_J \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbf{P}_J \in \mathbb{R}^{[6n+1+5n][6n+1+5n]}$ is the permutation matrix, $\mathbf{Q}_J \in \mathbb{R}^{6[6n+1+5n]}$ is an orthogonal matrix and $\mathbf{U}_J \in \mathbb{R}^{r_J \times r_J}$ is an invertible upper triangular matrix and r_J is the rank of \mathbf{J}_{all} . Substituting Eq. (15) into Eq. (16) leads to:

$$\delta\mathbf{e}_c = \mathbf{J}_{all}\mathbf{P}_J \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I}_{r_J} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \delta\xi_r \quad (17)$$

where $\delta\xi_r = \mathbf{J}_{rta}\delta\rho_{all}$ and $\mathbf{J}_{rta} = [\mathbf{I}_r \quad \mathbf{R}_j^{-1}\mathbf{A}_j] \mathbf{P}_J^\top$. After multiple measurements, the identification equation can be written as:

$$\delta\mathbf{e}_{c,set} = \mathbf{J}_{r,set}\delta\xi_r \quad (18)$$

where $\delta\mathbf{e}_{c,set} = [\delta\mathbf{e}_{c,1}^\top \quad \delta\mathbf{e}_{c,2}^\top \quad \dots \quad \delta\mathbf{e}_{c,m}^\top]^\top$, and $\mathbf{J}_{r,set} =$

$[\mathbf{J}_{all,1}^\top \quad \mathbf{J}_{all,2}^\top \quad \dots \quad \mathbf{J}_{all,m}^\top]^\top$. Based on the least square method, $\delta\xi_r$ can be expressed as:

$$\delta\xi_r = (\mathbf{J}_{r,set}^\top \mathbf{J}_{r,set})^{-1} \mathbf{J}_{r,set}^\top \delta\mathbf{e}_{c,set} \quad (19)$$

Figure 5: Flowchart of mixed error modeling and identification scheme.

Based on the Moore–Penrose formula, the error parameters $\delta\rho_{all}$ can be expressed as:

$$\delta\rho_{all} = \mathbf{J}_{rta}^T (\mathbf{J}_{rta} \mathbf{J}_{rta}^T)^{-1} \delta\xi_r \quad (20)$$

Based on Eq. (20), the scheme for error parameter identification is proposed, as shown in Figure 5. The angular transmission error $Q_s(q_e)$ of every joint is identified by spatial circle fitting and FFT if $R^2 > 0.8$. Then, all error parameters are identified based on Eqs. (19) and (20). This scheme will keep updating the values of $\mathbf{Q}_a(q_e)$ and ρ_g with updated $\delta\rho_{all}$ and re-executing the second step until $|\delta e_c|$ is less than the set value.

3. Case study of a 5-DOF hybrid robot

3.1. Structure description

A 5-DOF hybrid robot is taken as an example to validate the error modeling method. As shown in Figure 6, the hybrid robot consists of a 2-DOF serial mechanism and a 3-DOF parallel

Figure 6: Robot structure in CAD View.

mechanism. The parallel mechanism is composed of three-parallelogram architectures. The schematic diagram of the hybrid robot is shown in Figure 7, Joints C_1 and C_2 are driven by servomotor via rotary vector (RV) reducer, and joints C_3 and C_5 are driven by servomotor via harmonic reducers. Joint C_4 is driven by a servo motor via a harmonic drive and a timing belt. Three joints of the 3-DOF parallel mechanism are in a parallel state. Although this robot is a hybrid robot, the trajectory of the end-effector is still arc-shaped due to its special parallelogram mechanism when only one revolute joint moves. Besides, the robot has a small end area that can only be fitted with one laser tracker ball. So, only position information of the end-effector is measured. As shown in Figure 7, the base coordinate system $O - XYZ$ is attached to the base of the robot, and the moving coordinate system $o - xyz$ is attached to the end-effector. The 3-DOF parallel mechanism can drive the TCP to move along axes Z and Y and rotate around axis X through the three-parallelogram mechanism, and all the servomotors are in the $C_3(C_4C_5)$. For convenience of description, the robot is divided into the main branch (serial chain) and three parallelogram transmission mechanism. The main branch includes the joints C_1, C_2, C_3, C_8 and C_{13} . The three parallelogram mechanism are named based on their joints in vertices, $C_3C_6C_8C_9$, $C_3C_8C_{10}C_7$, and $C_8C_{11}C_{12}C_{13}$. Motor in joint C_3 drives the link between C_3 and C_8 , motor in joint C_4 drives the link between C_3 and C_6 , and motor in joint C_5 drives the link between C_3 and C_7 . Therefore, $C_3C_6C_8C_9$ is driven by the motors in C_3 and C_4 , $C_3C_7C_8C_{10}$ is driven by the motors in C_3 and C_5 , and $C_8C_{11}C_{12}C_{13}$ is driven by the output motion of $C_3C_6C_8C_9$ and $C_3C_7C_8C_{10}$. Based on the local POE method and Eq. (2), the screw coordinates of each joint in

Figure 8: The schematic diagram of the 5-DOF hybrid robot.

to the end of the parallelogram mechanism. According to analysis in section 2, the kinematic error model of the chains I and II can be directly written as:

$$\delta e_I = J_I \delta^I \rho + {}^I \Xi \delta^I q \quad (21)$$

$$\delta e_{II} = J_{II} \delta^{II} \rho + {}^{II} \Xi \delta^{II} q \quad (22)$$

where ${}^I \Xi = [{}^I \mu_1 {}^I \mu_2] \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 2}$; $\delta^I q = [\delta^I q_1 \delta^I q_2]^T$; ${}^{II} \Xi = [{}^{II} \mu_1 {}^{II} \mu_2 {}^{II} \mu_3] \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 3}$; $\delta^{II} q = [\delta^{II} q_1 \delta^{II} q_2 \delta^{II} q_3]^T$; ${}^{II} J \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 18}$; ${}^I J \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$

Superscript of the I and II means which chain the variable belongs to. Due to the closed-loop constraints of the parallel mechanism, the terminal errors δe_I and δe_{II} of chains I and II are the same, and unknowable passive joint errors $\delta^{II} q$ can be eliminated based on this constraint. Since the parallelogram mechanism is a planar mechanism, the value of the global screw ${}^I \mu_2$, ${}^{II} \mu_2$ and ${}^{II} \mu_3$ of joints ${}^I q_2$, ${}^{II} q_2$ and ${}^{II} q_3$ in parallelogram mechanism can be calculated as:

$${}^I \mu_2 = \begin{bmatrix} e_x \\ a \times e_x \end{bmatrix}; {}^{II} \mu_2 = \begin{bmatrix} e_x \\ b \times e_x \end{bmatrix}; {}^{II} \mu_3 = \begin{bmatrix} e_x \\ (b + c) \times e_x \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

where e_x is the unit vector norm to the plane that the parallelogram mechanism locates and has the same direction as the axis X_I , and a, b and c are the vectors of the links. a, b and c can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} [a^T, 1]^T &= {}^I g_0 u_1 [0, 0, l_{I1}, 1]^T \\ [b^T, 1]^T &= {}^{II} g_0 {}^{II} u_1 [0, 0, l_{II1}, 1]^T \\ [(b + c)^T, 1]^T &= {}^{II} g_0 {}^{II} u_1 {}^{II} g_1 {}^{II} u_2 [0, 0, l_{II2}, 1]^T \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

The ${}^{II} \tilde{\mu}$ that satisfy ${}^{II} \tilde{\mu}^T {}^{II} \mu_2 = 0$ and ${}^{II} \tilde{\mu}^T {}^{II} \mu_3 = 0$ can be used to eliminate redundant passive joint displacement errors $\delta^{II} q$ in Eq. (21), which can be written as:

$${}^{II} \tilde{\mu} = \begin{bmatrix} e_x \\ \frac{(b^T c - 1) b \times e_x}{(b^T c - 1) b^T b} \\ 12 \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

Based on Eq. (25), the error of joint^l q_2 can be derived as:

$$\delta^l q_2 = \mathbf{J}_{pi} \delta \rho_{pi} \quad (26)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_{pi} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\| \bar{\mu}^\top \mathbf{J} \|}{\| \bar{\mu}^\top \mu_2 \|}, -\frac{\| \bar{\mu}^\top \mathbf{J} \|}{\| \bar{\mu}^\top \mu_2 \|}, \frac{\| \bar{\mu}^\top \mu_1 \|}{\| \bar{\mu}^\top \mu_2 \|}, -\frac{\| \bar{\mu}^\top \mu_1 \|}{\| \bar{\mu}^\top \mu_2 \|} \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 14}$, and $\delta \rho_{pi} = [\delta^{\text{II}} \rho^\top, \delta^{\text{I}} \rho^\top, \delta^{\text{II}} q_1, \delta^{\text{I}} q_1]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{14 \times 1}$. Based on Eq. (26), the error model of the three-parallelogram mechanism can be expressed as:

$$\delta q_{4,m} = \mathbf{J}_{p1} \delta \rho_{p1}; \delta q_{5,mid} = \mathbf{J}_{p2} \delta \rho_{p2}; \delta q_{5,m} = \mathbf{J}_{p3} \delta \rho_{p3} \quad (27)$$

where subscript $p1$, $p2$ and $p3$ represents the chains $C_3 C_6 C_8 C_9$, $C_3 C_8 C_{10} C_7$, and $C_8 C_{11} C_{12} C_{13}$, respectively. Substituting Eq. (27) into Eq. (4) leads to the error model of the robot:

$$\delta \mathbf{e}_g = \mathbf{J}_g \delta \rho + \Xi_a \delta \mathbf{q} \quad (28)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_g = [\mathbf{J}_1, \mathbf{J}_2, \mathbf{J}_3, \mathbf{J}_4]$, $\Xi_a = [\mu_1, \dots, \mu_5] \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 5}$, $\mu_j = \text{Ad}(g_0 u_1 g_1 \dots u_j) \zeta_j$ ($j = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$), $\delta \rho = [\delta \rho_0^\top \dots \delta \rho_5^\top]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^{6 \times 6}$, $\delta \mathbf{q} = [\delta q_1, \delta q_2, \delta q_3, \delta q_{4m}, \delta q_{5m}]^\top \in \mathbb{R}^5$. In general, one target ball is attached to the end-effector and only the position information of the end-effector can be measured. Therefore, the error model can be written as[29]:

$$\delta \mathbf{e}_{gp} = \begin{bmatrix} -\mathbf{d} \times & \mathbf{I}_3 \end{bmatrix} \delta \mathbf{e}_g \quad (29)$$

where $\mathbf{d} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the vector from the robot base to the end-effector. Since only the position information of the end-effector is measured, the error identification equation can be written as:

$$\delta \mathbf{e}_{gp} = \mathbf{J}_g \delta \rho_{sp} + \Xi \delta \mathbf{q} \quad (30)$$

Substituting Eq. (30) into Eq. (15) leads to:

$$\delta \mathbf{e} = \mathbf{J}_g \delta \rho_{sp} + \Xi \mathbf{J}_q \delta \rho_q \quad (31)$$

Eq. (31) is the mixed error model(MEM) of the 5-DOF hybrid robot.

3.3. Experimental study

The experimental setup is shown in Figure 9. The measurement equipment is an AT-3 laser tracker with a measurement accuracy of $5 \mu\text{m}/\text{m}$ and only position information of the end-effector is measured. In the experiment, the Fourier series of angular transmission error of each joint is identified first. Since the parallelogram mechanism linkages are prone to interference with each other during motion, the safe individual rotation range of each joint of the 3-DOF parallel mechanism accounts for less than 1/10th of a circle. To enhance the stability of the fitting process, the spatial circle fitting with the center of circle calculated by nominal kinematics is used to identify the Fourier series of the angular transmission error of the last three joints (joints 3, 4 and 5). To prevent over-fitting, only the second-order Fourier series is used for fitting, which can be written as:

$$f(x) = a_0 + a_1 \sin(\omega x) + b_1 \cos(\omega x) + a_2 \sin(2\omega x) + b_2 \cos(2\omega x) \quad (32)$$

As shown in Table 2, the values of R^2 (Coefficient of determination) of joints 3 and 5 are above 0.8, and the value of R^2 of joint 4 is less than 0.5. This fitting result (as shown in Figure 10)

Figure 9: Experimental setup.

shows that the fluctuating behavior of the angular transmission error of joints 3 and 5 is relatively obvious. Therefore, only the fitting results of joints 3 and 5 are adopted, and the fitting error of their matching phase error and matching amplitude error are identified in the subsequent identification process. The R^2 of joint 4 is poor because it consists of a harmonic drive and a timing belt transmission. The elastic deformation and friction of the belt may interfere with the identification of the angular transmission error. After the fitting experiment of the Fourier series

Table 2: Fitting results of angular transmission error of each joint

	Joint3	Joint4	Joint5
R^2	0.9676	0.3679	0.8300
$a_0(10^{-6})$	6.421	0.7349	-0.5378
$a_1(10^{-4})$	5.454	0.1031	0.9239
$b_1(10^{-5})$	8.537	-6.633	1.788
$a_2(10^{-4})$	-1.119	0.4598	0.6319
$b_4(10^{-5})$	0.3784	-0.2094	0.2493
ω	102.8	101.9	101.9

of angular transmission error, the identification experiment for the mixed error model (MEM) is conducted. 56 measurement points are selected in the workspace, 28 of which are used as a test set and the others are used as a verification set. The initial position error of the robot is measured, and the maximum position error is about 15 mm(Labeled as INIT in Figure 11 and Table 4). To

Figure 10: Identification of Fourier series of angular transmission error of joint 3(a), joint 4(b) and joint 5 (c)

verify its advantages, the MEM is compared with the geometric error model(Labeled as GEM in Figures 11, 12 and Table 4)[8], the geometric error model combined with the backlash error model(BEM)[17, 18], and the BEM combined with the angular transmission error that only includes Fourier series (BEM+A). A summary of the identification methods used for comparative experiments and a comparison of error models is shown in Table 3. The comparative results

Table 3: A summary of the identification methods used for comparative experiments and a comparison of error models

Method	Joint Error Model	Identifiable Joint Errors
GEM[8]	$q_0 + q_e$	δq_0
BEM[17]	$q_0 + q_e - \text{sign}(q_{e,inc})q_{eb}$	$\delta q_0, \delta q_{eb}$
BEM+A	$q_0 + q_e - \text{sign}(q_{e,inc})q_{eb} + Q_s(q_e)$	$\delta q_0, \delta q_{eb}$
MEM*	$q_0 + q_e - \text{sign}(q_{e,inc})q_{eb} + Q_s(q_e)$	$\delta q_0, \delta q_{eb}, \delta Q_s(q_e)$

are shown in Figures 11 and 12. As shown in Table 4 and Figures 13, after the geometric error

Figure 11: Geometric error identification result

Figure 12: The identification experiment with different error models

identification with the geometric error model, the maximum position error of the robot is reduced from 15 mm to about 1 mm. The result of identification with BEM+A shows that the average position error on the test set is 0.1828mm, which has dropped by more than 20% compared with the BEM. However, it is worse than the identification result with BEM on the validation set, which shows that it is not accurate to only use the Fourier series of angular transmission error to compensate for the joint error. As contrast, the identification results of the MEM are the best in the experiment and the errors are dropped by more than 95% of initial errors , more than 50% compared with the geometric error model and more than 20% compared with the BEM, and both the test set's result and verification set result are better than BEM+A. In addition, the standard deviation of MEM is the smallest among the four methods mentioned above, demonstrating a better consistency of error in the new algorithm. The experimental results verify the effectiveness of the proposed error modeling method and identification scheme.

Table 4: Comparison of the identification effects of the hybrid error model and other error models(The percentages in parentheses in the table are the values that have decreased from the current value relative to the GEM

,units: mm)						
	Test Set			Validation Set		
	Average	Maximum	Std.Dev	Average	Maximum	Std.Dev
INIT	6.2789	14.9497	3.3010	6.1690	11.1584	2.6718
GEM[8]	0.4083	0.9443	0.2548	0.5458	1.0690	0.1986
BEM[17]	0.2148	0.4322	0.1069	0.2239	0.4579	0.1092
	(-47.39%)	(-54.23%)	(-58.04%)	(-58.98%)	(-57.12%)	(-45.02%)
BEM+A	0.1828	0.3549	0.0959	0.2255	0.4936	0.0986
	(-55.23%)	(-62.42%)	(-62.36%)	(-58.68%)	(-53.77%)	(-50.35%)
MEM*	0.1722	0.3476	0.0787	0.1675	0.3210	0.0836
	(-57.83%)	(-63.19%)	(-69.11%)	(-57.91%)	(-69.94%)	(-63.19%)

Figure 13: Comparison of the identification effects of the hybrid error model and other error models

4. Conclusions

In this paper, the comprehensive modeling of geometric error, backlash error and angular transmission error is studied. The matching error of these error model that interfere the comprehensive modeling are analyzed. The matching amplitude error and matching phase error are added into angular transmission error model to solve matching error problem. The angular transmission error and backlash error are then combined with the extended geometric error model in the form of joint errors to derive the MEM. In the identification process, the Fourier series of angular transmission error model is identified first, followed by the overall parameter identification based on MEM. Extensive experiments on the 5-DOF hybrid robot are carried out to demonstrate the precision and effective-ness of our method. The experiment on the 5-DOF hybrid robot show that the MEM is better than the geometric error model and BEM. MEM and identification scheme are suitable for robots with parallelogram mechanisms that have obvious angular transmission errors.

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